

SEMANTIC AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE TOURISTIC TERMS
IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *This article discusses the work carried out in our country during the development of tourism and research and their interdependence, the export of tourism services creates additional demand in the economy, provides employment and increases foreign exchange earnings.*

Keywords: *Tourism, countries, developing, visa, industry, foreign, world.*

Today, tourism is the main source of income for many developing countries. Exports of tourism services create additional demand in the economy, provide employment and increase foreign exchange earnings. Thus, the tourism sector plays an important role as a driving force of economic development. According to the World Tourism Organization, in 2018, exports of world tourism services increased by 4% to \$ 1.7 trillion, while the number of international tourist visits increased by 5% to 1.4 billion. The main reasons for this are low prices in developing countries and their simplification of visa procedures. Intensive work on the development of tourism in Uzbekistan in 2019 continued. In particular, a number of measures have been taken to simplify the visa process, eliminate unnecessary barriers and increase the investment attractiveness of the industry. As a result, in 2019, exports of tourism services increased by 26.1% compared to 2018 and amounted to \$ 1.3 billion, and the share of the industry in exports of services reached 39.3%. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" was adopted on July 18, 2019, which introduced new concepts based on the current stage of development of the industry, defined the principles and main directions of state policy in the field of tourism. Also, the subjects of tourist activity were divided into categories. The visa regime for citizens of 47 countries has been abolished and the number of countries with a visa-free regime has reached 86. In addition, in order to simplify the visa process, the number of countries that have the opportunity to obtain an electronic visa was 57. In addition, "Citizen", "Student", "Academic", "Pilgrim" and "Medical" visas were introduced. The analysis of the results of the work shows that the number of tourists visiting our country in 2019 increased by 26.2% compared to the previous period. The number of tourists visiting countries without a visa-free regime increased by 58%. As a result, the loading rate of tourist accommodation increased from 62% to 84%. In recent years, the development of the hostel market, which is in line with new trends in tourism and meets the requirements of a wide segment, is becoming increasingly important. To this end, in 2019, the procedure for mandatory certification of hostels was abolished and a number of other requirements were simplified in order to further stimulate the business of low-budget tourism infrastructure and hostels

in the country. The results did not wait long. In 2019 alone, 161 new hostels were built and commissioned in the country. They were able to serve 5,666 tourists at a time. In 2019, in accordance with the Regulations approved by the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 433, great emphasis was placed on the development of the hotel business. According to him, 40 million soums will be allocated from the state budget for each room of the newly built 3-star hotels, and 65 million soums for 4-star hotels. As a result of the work done, in 2019, a total of 277 new hotels were built and launched in the country. Reforms in the field of tourism are widely covered by foreign media. In particular, The Telegraph published a list of the most adventurous places on earth, and Uzbekistan took first place in this list. The Economist named Uzbekistan the country of the year. In addition, Lonely Planet, Harpers Bazaar, The Spectator and other publications have praised the country's tourism potential and made recommendations for reducing and developing shortcomings.

Although the tourism sector in Uzbekistan is relatively new, it has outperformed many other sectors. Our country has a great potential for the development of international tourism. Twenty years ago, no one knew Uzbekistan as a promising tourist destination. After gaining independence, the state has developed new principles in the field of tourism. On July 27, 1992, the National Company "Uzbektourism" was established by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main task of Uzbektourism is to implement state policy in the field of tourism and create a national model of tourism development. In addition, the national company coordinates the activities of all tourism organizations in the country, encourages the development of all areas of tourism, deals with staffing issues, attracts investment in the formation of the material and technical base and the development of infrastructure. Since 1993, our country has been a member of the International Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Since 2004, UNWTO's Office for Tourism Coordination on the Transcontinental Highway has been operating in Samarkand, the "heart" of the Great Silk Road. The government is working hard to modernize the tourism sector, improve the transport and hotel infrastructure in the country, as well as improve the regulatory framework for tourism. In order to promote tourism products abroad, the marketing project "Mega-info-tour" is being implemented for foreign tourism companies and the media. Such trips play an important role in expanding the tourist season, optimizing the flow of tourists to our country, as well as showing that each season in Uzbekistan is unique for tourists. In addition, the UNWTO-led International Silk Road Tourism Fair in Tashkent plays an important role in supporting Uzbekistan's tourism potential. The main purpose of the fair is to unite Uzbek and foreign experts in the field of tourism, to further expand professional cooperation between them. To date, this international fair is known as one of the largest exhibitions in Central Asia. The legendary past, the historical and engineering heritage of the Silk Road, the magnificent landscapes of nature, the local handicrafts passed down from generation to generation, the hospitality and human values of the people amaze and fascinate tourists and at the same time delight them. attracts people from all corners of Uzbekistan.

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